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REVIEW ARTICLE

Planetary View of COVID Impact vs. IQ & PISA Rank as National Level of Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

The time of COVID scare are memories of the past, and immediately after the democratic president took the power, in the US, suddenly COVID disappeared, and people got a novel more contagious virus, called "Ukrainite", that led to "super fertilization" of Ukraine's agricultural fields with all brands of "super-fertilizers", with immediate action, delivered under the form of TNT, PETN, C4, etc., with additional minor elements as P, C in Cyanides, S, Ag, Pt, K, Hg in fulminates, and much more, delivered by HIMARS, and Katyusha and tons of ordinary ammunition that will render them useless for agriculture, growing toxic crops, spiced with Pb, W, Ti, Ni because the chemical elements will be assimilated in the plants as a function of their chemical compatibility. The virus may be cured with a blow of reasoning or a Nuclear War, which may act as a supreme cure for the Planet, making it a better place, ready to roll the dices again and in 50 Million years to produce new evolved species, able to take the destiny in their hands and cure themselves. Meanwhile, in spite mainstream media bias, that ignored COVID for "political reasons", COVID is here to stay, and its spread and causalities on the planet are related to nations IQ and welfare as well as race, making the dependence very intricate. It is observed that the smart nations managed to minimize COVID effects, while most of OECD countries, in spite being rich, treated COVID as a business opportunity for big pharma, and contributed with record number at causalities. Meanwhile the virioli had a strange evolution that enhanced its propagation features making it a "cash-cow" for big pharma, while common knowledge acquired over centuries have been deliberately ignored.

Summary

The story of "gain of function" for various virioli started during at the beginning of XXs century, with military researches aimed in developing the so called bio-weapons. Once genetic code has been identified, with early understanding, military labs all around the world struggled to develop better genetically selective weapons. For these they need to understand human genetic code, and the differences that appear between various ethnic groups or even in individual's families. In the same time the "Ukrainite" "virus" has been developed, after a very long incubation period, starting from 1993, when a "Philanthropic" oligarch [1] discovered that East European countries may be used as proxy agents for NATO, taking the body-bags burden, if their leaders are appropriately

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selected and stimulated and the nation armed and indoctrinated well in order to attack and submit Russia, for the benefit of military industrial complex stake-holders [2]. The incubation process started by 2014, but had frozen during Covid pandemic initial year, but the agonizing failure of neo-colonial hegemony, accelerated it and transformed it into a much larger and dangerous pandemic where the ultimate cure lies in hands of the military-nuclear complex [3,4]. Meanwhile the graciously ignored pandemic continues to thrive, being helped in keeping hospitals busy by normal airborne “cold” viruses and respiratory bacterial infections, transmitted and by skin contact. At this point an observation has to be made about the sensitivity to mask wearing of the “cold” viruses that are small nano-machines of 20-30 nm in diameter, being more sensitive to propagation hazards than SARS-CoV-2 that is a larger nano-machine of about 100 nm in diameter. After politicizing the pandemic, when masks have been eliminated the small viruses appeared again more virulently, and new vaccines were required. The occurrence of SARS-CoV-2 remained a mystery, while the facts in public knowledge are the following:

- By mid-2019 a strange disease called EVALI appeared, briefly killed more than 50 people in the US, the blame was put on JUUL for its THC vaping doses, and was “pushed under the rug”, being “forgotten”.
- By the end of 2019, as a “coincidence” the virus erupted in Wuhan, in the near vicinity of a biological laboratory, funded by WMO, where US representatives, funded them to research possible “gain of function” of a bat virus to become human compatible like SARS-CoV-2, but later evidences declined to prove that virus originated there.
- Starting from January 2020 virus exploded all around Earth, and big Pharma got substantial advantages in producing a vaccine while in the US the protection against virus using efficient pandemic control measures become an issue of “political statement”, and due to that with less than 4% of world population US contributed with over 25% of causalities behaving 6 times dumber than the world’s avg.
- During Trump 1/2 million US citizens died, and Biden came into power and under his watch another 3/4 mn and counting died, proving that

Caucasian brain “is not cabled” to understand the threat from aerosolized watery droplets airborne propagation of Nano particulates and protect against.

- During 2021-23 period, the virus suffered many mutations, more than 4 vaccinations being needed to reach an average immunity, but still being infected by the new variants, while “big-pharma” made good profits and thinking about:...” the virus keeps mutating? Well, one of the things we’re exploring is, like, why don’t we just mutate it ourselves so we could preemptively develop new vaccines, right?” Walker, a Pfizer R&D director openly admits [5].

Well in this scenario we lost the military bio labs connections [6], and with what we learned from mainstream mass media suffering of “Ukrainite”, the Chinese might know something and might be right, but are in the same situation with Germany’s will to honestly name the terrorist in the case of North Stream gas pipe sabotage. Of course this is classified material, and if it didn’t clogged any toilet in Delaware, we might learn by 2100+ how was the real history, which will bring nothing new to public knowledge, which is used to “follow the money” and “connect the dots”.

Results and Discussion

Using statistical data available on Internet as World odometer/COVID [7], from where the data about total number of cases, death and vaccinations per 1 mn people have been collected. In order to plot them in the chart the data have been processed and rescaled. Maximum and minimum for the analyzed data set of 109 countries we had the IQ rank of each country represented on abscises, where near the axis the country name is written. In the legend on the yellow rectangle on the right side is given the maximum and minimum of each value and the legend symbol. The IQ data [8,9] and selected the first 109 countries. IQ (Intelligence Quotient) is a quantitative assessment of the human intellect level: the level of intelligence relative to the average person of the same age. It is defined by special tests. Simply speaking, the IQ test measures your ability to solve problems and reasoning. There are various tests analyzing your visual and mathematical skills, knowledge of the language, memory, concentration and so on all over the world. They are created by qualified psychologists

and specialists. In conclusion, you get a score—a score of your abilities. According to the talented expert Mensa Lisa Van Gemert, people with a high level of intelligence can control this world and manipulate people much better than others.

IQ is really a test with the help of which you can compare yourself with other people. The normalized IQ-to rank countries was used to list the countries, and was printed with green triangles on 2nd diagonal.

During 2020 due to COVID travel restrictions many countries did not took part, and we have used the average results based ranking of the country [10], and ranking have been normalized in% in a 0-100 scale, and represented on chart with blue diamonds. We observe that most of them are grouped in a cone outside the IQ ranking line. The abatement of a PISA point from IQ point of a country placed on diagonal line represents in fact the difference in IQ of the present generation, with green triangle, and the future generation represented by PISA point with blue-diamond on the same ordinate axis tell us how the future generation, over 10 y, will be (smarter or Dumber) compared to actual generation intelligence level. The statistical PISA assembly being so small we amplified by a factor of 4 PISA results that usually are in the vicinity of IQ zone, as you see the dashed arrows that shows that the next generations has the trend to become dumber than actual one, and most of US-EU countries have real issues in the education that drives to these results. The so called “US/Western Education vortex” that became visible due to amplification, that moved it outside the real position, represents a strong worrying trend in the actual education that became more a business, than a social service, where the education units have lowered the standards to keep the student happy and make a profit. For many countries that were included in vortex, it is clear that the next generation may be up to 60% dumber in a decade than the actual population. These calculations consider the amplification effect due to small statistical sampling group and have to be revisited and corrected when new results will come out.

For understanding COVID we also plotted the percent of death dividing the number of deaths to the number of infected people from 1 mn people. Vaccination rate was also represented on the same scale taking as reference “zero” the value 100, and growing upwards, towards zero. This process is important for one seeking to understand if the tests have been useful or not. We observe that the countries

were divided in 5 blocks: the super smart countries “A” comprising the following countries:

Hong Kong	South Korea	Japan	Netherlands	Switzerland
Singapore	Taiwan	China	North Korea	Iceland

located in the blue square representing 90% (percentiles). Among them are Chinese entities where only the “Main Land”, managed to keep causalities at their minimum, by applying the pandemic control measures a little at the extreme, but were scared by the tune-up of the virus on their genetic code, as one may see from death rate that is 2-3 times higher than for the countries in the “B” block. The smart countries, in “B” class are rich, developed countries from US and EU and they are in rank order:

Canada	Austria	Norway	Mongolia	Italy
Macao	Germany	Sweden	France	Latvia
Finland	New Zealand	Denmark	Hungary	Poland
Belgium	Australia	Czechia	United States	Russia
United Kingdom	Luxembourg	Estonia	Spain	Croatia

Some “paradoxes become visible in these groups, when one looks and compare the total no. of cases, to death rate, testing rate and income. Looking to income distribution, brown-circular dots, one may observe that the countries in “A”, “B” groups are rich, so they bought a lot of testing kits, but that did not helped them to prevent infection, and nor the vaccination campaign. As the total no. of cases rate shows, the infection rate from 50% and reached up to 64% of population except for the Chinese entities.

The testing rate reached up to 20 pcs/person for Austria that also had a record in class “B” for infection rate, showing that testing only without quarantine measures and a smart population able to follow instructions and trust the government is useless. So the countries in the group B are the most infected in spite they had enough vaccines and test kits. Looking at death rate trend, it is visible that it grows for the poor and uneducated countries. The record is reached by countries as Afghanistan, due to destruction, debacle and genocide induced by US and by “frizzing”/stealing the money deposited in US banks and sabotaging their national medicine. The European Union is about to sign a deal for 1.8 billion doses of the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine after a dispute with AstraZeneca derailed its vaccination campaign, and rumors point towards corruption and bribery at the highest level [11]. Looking for trends we observe

that when IQ decreases; income decreases too, and death rate is increasing. WE also observe the total infection rate groups states in 6 categories, aligning after lines as G1; G3; G5 for which when IQ decreases (rank in the hierarchy increases) the total infection rate to decrease too. Being on a function: Infection Rate (i:IQ; etc.) = $\delta(IQ)G^I IQ$; where G^I , δ are complex, multi-parameter functions, while $\delta(IQ)$ may be a genetic hidden parameter function that acts as a Kronecker δ or a Dirichlet function. Learning more, that potential fit, may tell us what hidden features countries like South Korea, Netherlands, UK, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Ukraine, Vietnam, Venezuela have in common from genetic point of view, that may have connections with visible parameter as IQ, Income, Temperature, etc. and might be different from Macao, Ukraine, Malaysia, Romania, Turkey, and Bahrein, that are connected on a near orthogonal function, where Ukraine is a common point. Learning about genes and their macroscopic behavioral effects, will be a future subject for “Big Data”, Artificial Intelligence” research, and may be a one important step forward of building genetically selective bio-weapons, if “planetary mind” is set on self-destruction purposes, of a very important advancement in curative medicine based on genetic programming, able to improve human structure, using technologies derived from the actual mRNA, where the mRNA is a type of molecule that has the ability to deliver a specific set of instructions to your cells to make pieces of protein used by certain viruses. This could induce an immune response to fight off a viral attack, but with further advances it may “gain in functionality”, and may do even more up to modifying DNA in the desired direction; good or bad.

One has to understand that present presentation is not accurate, because each country has an intrinsic ethnic and cultural diversity that was not covered by macroscopic parameters that were used in this analysis. The infection rate data used in this is under evaluated, because starting from mid-2022 the interest of tracking COVID evolution decreased, due to political reasons, as the global business goals of the big Pharma have been accomplished, and was the time to launch a novel disease, “Ukrainite”, where two Slavic nations are killing each other, for the benefit of Military-Industrial stake owners, from “Global West”, where NATO is a tool of domination. This virus is a precursor of a series of new virus mutants as “Tawanite” and “Irannite” that are in preparation, in order to “master the Future” of the planet serving

the interest of the “Davos Group” to maintain their hegemonic advantages, at high risk and large causalities and destructive impact on environment. The roots of this manifestation is correlated with the performance in the class “B” of nations that failed to understand and use appropriate methods to control pandemic, proving that the present IQ test as is made, is biased, in the favor of West Europe and US, which by this bad response to pandemic proved that their place is not at all in class “B” = smart, but in a lower class “C” = average or “D” = Dumb. The lower mortality rate may be due to their high income with better hospital care and abundance of treatment options and medication. Starting with a new IQ quotient one may define the National “BRAIN POWER” that is simply obtained by multiplying the average IQ with Population. This function gives for China NBP (China) = $\langle IQ \rangle \times Pop = 148 \text{ GIQu}$ (Giga IQ units), for USA, NBP (US) = 33 GIQu, with a 30% downgrade due to COVID response = 20 GIQu, for India NBP (India) = 110 GIQu. In this condition was clear that the US will naturally fall on the 4th place, in world economic power, after EU, but launching the “Ukrainite” over EU, they succeeded to subducted EU by 1-2% in their GDP loses, therefore, until the EU countries will grow some brain, will fall into 4th position.

The “Davosite bacteriologic infection”, is retarded, because on PISA tests one looks of expenses per student realizes that what one is obtaining by investing \$1 in the US, obtains with \$ 1/4 in France (also a rank over 30th) and with only 5 cent in China, but well there is no conversion from 1st place to > 30th place. IN fact, in real value China is the first world economy since 20 years ago, and only artificial FIAT currency makes it look 2nd. That is why “Taiwanite” is on the launching pad, but postponed because “Ukrainite”, complications that will trigger the “Davosite” cure with “nuclear pills”, making old dream of MacArthur to separate Korea from China using the 24, at that time nuclear charges US had, with Co to make a 200 y radioactive barrier 30 miles wide, will be realized in Ukraine, near Polish border, and may be N near Finland’s border, with dire consequences for environment, and even the “masters of the future will realize that their fortunes may become dust, as well anticipate in the “Planet of the Apes” movie. Launching the “Taiwanite” virus too soon, will give better chances that the fiction of the movie to become a world reality. As one may see in figure 1, the “B” class countries, the active promoters of these odd viruses, based on old concept of “divide and domina”, were unable to protect themselves against a more mild infection by aerosolized neutral

Figure 1 Holistic view on COVID effects in the world and potential correlation functions.

watery nano-droplets, containing the virioli, where the threat came from another person that might be an asymptomatic noncontagious. In the conditions of a nuclear exchange, those who survived to primary effects, have now to protect against radioactive, chemically toxic nano-powders, sometime containing cocktails of mutated virioli, in the context of almost all infrastructures cascading, basically meaning, no medicine, no protective equipment, no food or shelter against nature elements. It may be a very “interesting” end of business, much worse as the 4th place in the multipolar world. If SARS-CoV-2 was a real virus, the last virioli we discussed are virtual-virioli, that infected EU-US minds, being unable of using common sense, and see the truth.

From civilization point of view, we may say that took planet 5000 y from stone age to iron age, to industrial revolution, and by 20th century we enter in self destruction age, while by 21st century we reach the genetic programming edge overlapping self-destruction age. From here, planet may return to protozoa age, or calm down and progress to an inter-stellar age, mankind learning to live on few Kg of Plutonium or D⁶Li similar to how today we live on a

tank with gasoline, or a little bit better, developing an environmentally friendly and seamless economy.

Conclusion

The lessons learned analyzing the chart in figure 1 are the following:

- Low IQ triggers low income, had lower SARS-CoV-2 lower infection rate due to reduced people travel and human interchange, but has high death rate due to poor medicine and testing rate.
- For US and EU countries, also known as “common west”, including Australia, Japan and SKorea, the higher testing rate and vaccinations were useless in preventing the infection rate, and had almost ¾ of population infected by various variants of COVID.
- Testing worked as exceptions for China and India that applied known complementary measures to control pandemic and were open to all possible medical and physiological alternatives.

- The “common west” countries put big-pharma business first, over their populations health, and were weak in understanding the threat and protecting against it, proving the their IQ quotient is inflated, by their manipulation and customization of the test; a corrected IQ is required that to consider the capabilities of a nation to respond to natural or man-made disasters and prevail; most of these countries has to be downgraded by about 30%.
- Some affinities among various countries have been observed that have intricate connections that will represent a subject for future research involving big-data, Artificial Intelligence and genetic coding in bio-engineered systems.
- The COVID evolution was like “Shock and Awe” starting with a more lethal variant, that via mutation becomes milder and more contagious leaving room for “good business”, but is unclear if this evolution was genetically programed or it is the result of mutation under natural selection action.
- There are also other virtual-viruses mainstream, controlled mass-media borne and virtual bacteria transmitted by contact with any form of currency or treasure that is infecting human minds, being capable of triggering large planetary disasters, if not applied a preemptive cure, having the roots in the low, real IQ and moral values of the “Common West” populations, which are the most bellicose and the less fit to survive the consequences of their aggression.
- A degradation trend in education was also observed, that is dangerous, driving to higher sensitivity to virtual disease and infections, with high chances of self-destruction ignorance enabled.
- High IQ, high income assured a high infection rate, with lower death rate, but high number of deaths, in spite of high testing and vaccination rate, that proved useless, and just business when population was subjected to multi-dimensional information propagation

and their leaders misinformation politicized campaign with some exceptions from a few smarter countries who applied simultaneously other engineered pandemic controls.

- Quality of data has been affected due to politics interference for the sake of big-business. The big FIAT money release on the market with the purpose to dilute the value of USD, by inflation in order to reduce the absolute value of the closed transactions, involving funds that had to be returned.
- Wearing masks in proximity of another person is a good mutual protection measure, suppressing the propagation of small virioli, as SARS-CoV-1, Flu, etc., while washing hands and disinfecting surfaces is a good practice to prevent bacterial infections and respiratory diseases.

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